

APPENDIX 1

P1.1 Survey questionnaire for students from 5th to 8th grade of elementary school

Dear student!

Here is a questionnaire designed to explore the factors that influence your career decision-making. Your responses are confidential and will not be shared with anyone who could identify you. The questionnaire uses male grammatical forms, which apply to both genders. Your answers mean a lot to us, so please make an effort to complete the questionnaire enthusiastically to the end.

The authors of the research

I. Demography:

1. Gender:
a) male b) female
2. Grade:
a) 5. b) 6. c) 7. d) 8. e) 9.
3. The name of your school: _____

II. Your dream job:

1. Which is your dream job? _____
2. Why: _____
3. Which schools you would need to finish in order to do this job: _____

III. Career aspirations:

For each of the listed occupations on a scale from 1 (do not want it at all) to 7 (very much want to do it), indicate how strongly you want to pursue it when you grow up. If you are not familiar with the occupation, choose the option "do not know the occupation." All listed occupations apply to both genders. Mark only one number for EACH of the occupations listed below.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Do not know the occupation.	Do not want it at all.	Do not want it.	I'd rather not do it.	I am not determined.	Maybe I want to do it.	I want to do it.	Very much want to do it.

Occupations that require a university degree

- a) Occupations in the military or police (e.g. officer, police officer...)
- b) Technical and technological professions (e.g. mechanical engineer, civil engineer, electrical engineer, computer engineer...)
- c) Mathematical and natural science professions (e.g. biologist, chemist, physicist, pharmacist...)
- d) Professions in the social sciences and humanities (e.g. archaeologist, historian, geographer, translator, psychologist...)
- e) Professions in healthcare (e.g. doctor, dentist...)
- f) Occupations in education (e.g. teacher, educator...)
- g) Professions in sports and culture (e.g. musician, actor, writer, sports coach...)
- h) Professions in law (e.g. lawyer, judge...)
- i) Official, manager, economist

j) Professions in agriculture (e.g.: agronomist, veterinarian, livestock farmer...)

Occupations that require a high school education

a) Technical professions (e.g.: painter, bricklayer, mechanic, mechatronics, toolmaker, electrician, carpenter...)

b) Professions in healthcare (eg: nurse/medical technician...)

c) Office occupations (e.g. secretary...)

d) Professions in catering, tourism and trade (e.g.: waiter, cook, hairdresser, trader, driver...)

e) Professions in agriculture (e.g.: farmer, forester...)

Other:

Professions that require completed elementary school

a) Simple technical occupations (e.g.: machine and device operator, technical worker...)

b) Simple jobs (e.g. cleaner, kitchen assistant, sweeper...)

Other:

IV. What level of education do you intend to achieve?

Mark the highest level of education you intend to achieve:

a) complete the elementary school

b) complete the secondary school

c) complete the university degree

d) another (what education you intend to achieve): _____

V. Occupation of parents

1. The occupation of the father (stepfather/guardian): _____
2. The occupation of the mother (stepmother/guardian): _____

P1.2 Survey questionnaire for 9th grade students of elementary school

Dear student!

Here is a questionnaire designed to explore the factors that influence your career decision-making. Your responses are confidential and will not be shared with anyone who could identify you. The questionnaire uses male grammatical forms, which apply to both genders. Your answers mean a lot to us, so please make an effort to complete the questionnaire enthusiastically to the end.

The authors of the research

I. Demography:

1. Gender:

a) male b) female

2. The name of your school: _____

3. Academic achievement

Please indicate your academic performance in the following subjects last year:

Sufficient 2 Good 3 Very good 4 Excellent 5

a) math

b) mother tongue

c) first foreign language _____

4. Approximately how many books do you have at home? (ignore magazines, newspapers and school textbooks)

a) nothing or very little (0–10)

b) approximately for one bookshelf (11–25)

c) approximately for one bookcase (26–100)

d) approximately for two bookcases (101–200)

e) approximately for three or more bookcases (more than 200 books).

II. Your dream job:

1. Which is your dream job? _____

2. Why: _____

3. Which schools you would need to finish in order to do this job: _____

III. Personal factors for career choice

The following questions refer to the profession you want to choose. On a scale from 1 (not true at all) to 7 (completely true), indicate to what extent each factor influences your choice of profession:

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
	Not true at all	Very wrong	Not true	Neither true nor false	True	Very true	Absolutely true

- a) ... for which I will easily be able to complete the required education.
- b) ... where I will be interested in working.
- c) ... which I will enjoy.
- d) ... which offers challenges.
- e) ... which requires group work.
- f) ... with which I help others.
- g) ... which will fulfill my life's ambitions.
- h) ... which others have advised me.
- i) ... which is well paid.
- j) ... which provides enough quality employment opportunities.
- k) ... which allows for a lot of travel.
- l) ... which takes place in a clean environment.
- m) ... which is performed outdoors.
- n) ... which enables employment in the hometown.
- o) ... which is physically demanding.
- p) ... which is mentally demanding.
- q) ... which requires special talents.
- r) ... of which people I respect

- have a good opinion.
 - s) ... which will raise my reputation.
 - t) ... which will make me famous.
 - u) ... for which I am willing to study hard.
 - v) ... which I will get to as quickly as possible.
 - w) ... in which I will have to constantly educate myself.
 - x) ... in which I will manage other employees.
 - y) ... in which I will teach other employees.
 - z) ... in which I will invest additional energy in advancement.
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IV. Attitude toward technical professions

We are particularly interested in your attitude towards technical professions (e.g. mechanical engineering, electronics, construction, architecture, etc.). Mark where your opinion is on the scale between two statements.

Technical occupations:

- | | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 | 6 | 7 | |
|--|---|---|---|---|---|---|---|---|
| a) ... are very uninteresting | | | | | | | | ... are very interesting. |
| b) ... offer no challenges at all. | | | | | | | | ... offer many challenges. |
| c) ... are very disrespected. | | | | | | | | ... are highly respected. |
| d) ... are very unimportant. | | | | | | | | ... are very important. |
| e) ... are for men only. | | | | | | | | ... are only for women. |
| f) ... are very poorly paid. | | | | | | | | ... are very well paid. |
| g) ... do not provide employment opportunities at all. | | | | | | | | ... provide great employment opportunities. |
| h) ... do not require constant education at all. | | | | | | | | ... require a lot of continuous education. |
| i) ... are not physically demanding at all. | | | | | | | | ... are very physically demanding. |
| j) ... sploh niso umsko zahtevni. | | | | | | | | ... are not mentally demanding at all. |

k) Education for a technical profession is undemanding.
l) People I respect have a bad opinion of technical careers.
m) ... does not raise reputation.

Education for a technical profession is very demanding.
People I respect have good opinions about technical careers.
... raise reputation.

V. Intention to choose a technical profession

On a scale from 1 (not at all true) to 7 (completely true), mark the extent to which each statement applies to you:

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
	Not true at all	Very wrong	Not true	Neither true nor false	True	Very true	Absolutely true
a) I am very seriously considering getting a technical career.							
b) I am determined to acquire a technical profession.							
c) I am willing to do anything to get a technical career.							
d) My goal in life is to get a technical profession.							
e) My dream job is in the field of technology.							

VI. Information about the secondary school to which you applied

Which high school did you apply to?

- a) General gymnasium
- b) Technical gymnasium
- c) Other type of gymnasium
- d) 4-year professional school
- e) 2 or 3-year secondary vocational school

If you chose gymnasium: I chose gymnasium because.....

- ... I don't know what I want to become, so I get a few years to decide.... želim nadaljevati šolanje na fakulteti.
- ... because of my parents.
- ... it is the most prestigious school.
- Other:

VII. Occupation of parents

1. The occupation of the mother (stepmother/guardian): _____
2. The occupation of the father (stepfather/guardian): _____

VI. Career aspirations:

For each of the listed occupations on a scale from 1 (do not want it at all) to 7 (very much want to do it), indicate how strongly you want to pursue it when you grow up. All listed occupations apply to both genders. Mark only one number for EACH of the occupations listed below.

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Do not want it at all.	Do not want it.	I'd rather not do it.	I am not determined.	Maybe I want to do it.	I want to do it.	Very much want to do it.

Occupations that require a university degree

- a) Occupations in the military or police (e.g. officer, police officer...)
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- d) Professions in the social sciences and humanities (e.g. archaeologist, historian, geographer, translator, psychologist...)
- e) Professions in healthcare (e.g. doctor, dentist...)
- f) Occupations in education (e.g. teacher, educator...)
- g) Professions in sports and culture

(e.g. musician, actor, writer, sports coach...)
h) Professions in law (e.g. lawyer, judge...)
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j) Professions in agriculture (e.g.: agronomist, veterinarian, livestock farmer...)

Occupations that require a high school education

a) Technical professions (e.g.: painter, bricklayer, mechanic, mechatronics, toolmaker, electrician, carpenter...)
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Other:

Professions that require completed elementary school

a) Simple technical occupations (e.g.: machine and device operator, technical worker...)
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Other:
